

ENERGY RESOURCES OF THE EARTH'S CRUST: CHALLENGES OF THE MODERN ECONOMY

Original article

Demonstration of the importance of preprocessing the text fields of bibliometric records to identify promising research tasks: Case study of Scopus data on Petroleum Reservoir Engineering

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Abstract. *Background.* Nowadays, bibliometric analysis of data from abstract databases is often used to identify relevant research tasks in order to rationalize the use of financial and other resources. *Objective.* To demonstrate the importance of preprocessing the text fields of bibliometric records to build a network of co-occurrence of terms and the possibility of subsequent use of Scimago Graphica for detailed study of different slices of clustering results in order to identify relevant research topics. *Materials and methods.* A total of 8,051 records exported from Scopus and matching the filter: (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD, "Petroleum Reservoir Engineering")) for the last ten years were used. VOSviewer and Scimago Graphica programs have been applied for bibliometric analysis. *Results.* The study showed the relevance of using the filter "LIMIT-TO EXACTKEYWORD" in the query to Scopus; the expediency of disclosing abbreviations in the text fields of records and preliminary clarification of texts; the effectiveness of using filters in the program Scimago Graphica to build a network of conjugation of terms in order to identify promising research topics. *Conclusions.* The promising research topics identified by the analysis can be described by the following terms: 1) nanopores, shale oil, pore size, molecular; 2) nanoparticles and nanofluids; 3) methane hydrate, hydrate saturation, hydrate bearing sediments. It is observed that in some cases, terms occurring in the same cluster are not the best choice for querying to expand the collection of publications on a given topic. Therefore, a separate study is proposed for this purpose using Apriori class algorithms.

Keywords: terms co-occurrence, text preprocessing, abbreviations, promising research tasks, VOSviewer, Scimago Graphica

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Introduction

Assessment of the significance of tasks within a given theme can contribute to the rational use of financial, human and other resources necessary for scientific research. Bibliometric analysis of data from abstract databases can serve as a basis for such assessments.

As an example of publications that reflect the above, the following works can be cited.

The paper [1] argues that peer review decisions provide >95% of the funding for academic medical research, so it is important to understand the effectiveness of peer review and how it can be improved.

The allocation of research funding relies on peer review, which can be biased. A study [2] analyzes interventions in peer review and decision-making to improve research funding practices.

Recently, funding agencies have begun to call for more research into improving funding allocation processes and seeking effective mechanisms for allocating research funds [3].

Currently, VOSviewer is the most widely used program for bibliometric research [4]. For example, according to a query to The Lens open abstract database, for the period from 1 January 2020 to 4 January 2025, the number of scholarly works in which the term VOSviewer appears in the “Title”, “Abstract”, “Keyword” or “Field of Study” fields was 15,526, while CiteSpace appears in 8,105 and Bibliometrix in 3,122 works.

However, the number of publications dealing with preprocessing of text fields, such as “Author Keywords” or “Abstracts”, is quite rare.

For example, if we add the term “lemmatization” to the previous query about VOSviewer, we find only one book chapter [5] and one article [6], in which the authors analyze bibliometric data from Scopus and Web of

Science on digital transformation, cleaned by lemmatization and stemming, and the article by the author of the present paper [7].

This is not to say that a more detailed search in more abstract databases will not find such publications, but only to point out that the use of VOSviewer in combination with text field preprocessing is rare and can be considered an underappreciated but important task. On the other hand, the preprocessing of texts is a classic task in text analysis [8].

In this paper, bibliometric data are sequentially analyzed using VOSviewer and Scimago Graphica to identify relevant research problems. No publications by other authors were found in which the parameters obtained from VOSviewer were used to filter the data and construct coordinate axes in Scimago Graphica program.

The above has defined the objectives of this study related to using VOSviewer for bibliometric analysis, which are to:

- Analyze some features of the fields “Author Keywords” and “Index Keywords”, which are valuable for clustering of terms based on their co-occurrence.

- Show the importance of disclosing abbreviations in text preparation before keyword clustering.

- Show the importance of preprocessing the text fields of bibliometric records.

- Provide an example of the usefulness and benefits of using abstract texts to identify topical issues through the case study of Petroleum Reservoir Engineering research in comparison to the Author keywords.

- Demonstrate the possibilities of using the Scimago Graphica program for detailed examination in the coordinates “average time of publication” – “average citation” of different slices of clustering results in order to identify relevant research topics.

Materials and methods

The Scopus data (8,051 records) corresponding to the query: (SUBJAREA(ENER) AND PUBYEAR > 2013 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD, "Petroleum Reservoir Engineering")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar"))) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) current as of 16 November 2024, was used as a basis for the analysis to identify relevant research challenges and to demonstrate some features of the bibliometric records that are useful to consider in doing so¹.

Key characteristics of the sample

If we use the field "Author Keywords" for term clustering, it should be noted that in the sample under consideration this field is not filled in 1,470 cases out of a total of 8,051 records.

At the same time, all records of the "Index Keywords" field are filled, and each record is assigned from 20 to 30 tags.

In the query used, the term "Petroleum Reservoir Engineering" was specified in the "Keywords" field. A direct search in the data exported from Scopus showed that this term occurs in all entries of the "Index Keywords" field, once in the "Author Keywords" field and 5 times in the "Abstract" field.

According to Scopus Support Center, "Indexed keywords are chosen by Scopus and are standardized to vocabularies derived from thesauri that Elsevier owns or licenses. Unlike author keywords, indexed keywords take into account synonyms, various spellings, and plurals"².

"Standardized vocabularies" actually determines what labels Scopus assigns to a given bibliometric record in the "Index Keywords" field.

Thus, by using LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD, "Petroleum Reservoir Engineering") in the query, we significantly expand the output of records classified by Scopus on the topic of interest. This is important when there is an interest in enhancing the context of the topic of interest, allowing us to analyze what knowledge can be used to extend the topic under study. A promising topic should have a broad research area that can be exploited as a resource.

However, while expanding the sample, it is desirable to ensure that it remains relevant to the topic under study, so below are some characteristics of the sample used in the paper to demonstrate its appropriateness to the stated topic "Petroleum Reservoir Engineering".

The most frequent values of the SUBJECT AREA field from the file Scopus_exported_refine_values.csv are the following: Energy (8,051), Earth and Planetary Sciences (4,475), Chemical Engineering (1,854), Engineering (1,375), Chemistry (1,043), Mathematics (779), Environmental Science (463).

The most frequent values of the SOURCE TITLE field from the file Scopus_exported_refine_values.csv are the following: Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering (1,627), Energy and Fuels (669), Fuel (588), Energies (581), Journal of Natural Gas Science and Engineering (475), Journal of Petroleum Exploration and Production Technology (358), Petroleum Science and Technology (283), Geoenergy Science and Engineering (254), SPE Journal (238), Energy (173), International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control (150), Energy Sources Part A Recovery Utilization and Environmental Effects (148).

¹ Supplementary materials for this article are available via Figshare:
<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28524263.v1>

² Scopus Support Center. URL:
https://service.elsevier.com/app/answers/detail/a_id/21730/supporthub/scopus/kw/index+keywords+field/ (accessed 20 February 2025).

The most frequent values of the KEYWORD field from the file Scopus_exported_refine_values.csv are the following: Petroleum Reservoir Engineering (8,051), Petroleum Reservoirs (3,941), Hydrocarbon Reservoir (1,965), Oil Well Flooding (1,588), Permeability (1,536), Fracture (1,485), Enhanced Recovery (1,379), Carbon Dioxide (1,266), Crude Oil (1,252), Enhanced Oil Recovery (1,237), Gases (1,180), Low Permeability Reservoirs (1,139), Porosity (1,084), Reservoirs (water) (1,070).

The above field values are in good agreement with the Petroleum Reservoir Engineering theme. This indicates the adequacy of the sample used for the analysis.

Although the term “Petroleum Reservoir Engineering” rarely appears in the text fields of the articles themselves (Title, Abstract, Author Keywords), the tags (Index Keywords) assigned to the articles by Scopus can be used to create queries to the database.

The most frequent values of the COUNTRY field from the file Scopus_exported_refine_values.csv are the following: China (4,359), United States (1,496), Iran (754), Canada (593), United Kingdom (358), Australia (348), Saudi Arabia (226), Russian Federation (191), Brazil (169), India (150), Norway (131), France (121), Germany (117).

The publications of Russian researchers are underrepresented in international journals; for example, Iran has been under sanctions for a long time, but has much more international publications. Certainly, Russia has many high-quality journals on oil and gas, but English-language publications also fulfill a marketing role to promote the interests of research groups. For example, China, with 4,359 publications, is comparable to the sum of the publications of the other countries in this list – 4,654.

To participate in international projects, not only scientific but also industrial, it is crucial to promote the country’s technologies and competencies and to establish contacts. The identification of technological capabilities of advanced competencies is largely based on the analysis of scientific literature [9], which determines the importance of publications in international journals.

Scientific publications play a vital role in promoting and ensuring energy security by providing critical insights, frameworks and data that inform policy decisions [10].

This study is limited by the use of author keywords and text abstracts to identify relevant research tasks related to the topic “Petroleum Reservoir Engineering” and the importance of preprocessing the text fields.

Methods and programs in use

The following programs were used for bibliometric analysis: VOSviewer [4] and Scimago Graphica [11].

In preparing the data for analysis, a list of abbreviations occurring in the author keywords was compiled. The 80 most frequent abbreviations were expanded to their full names.

When creating a list of abbreviations, there may be ambiguous abbreviations that were not considered in our case, e.g., ES → effective stress, effective simulation.

Identified author keywords differing only in plural or singular are reduced to singular. Keywords distinguished by the presence or absence of a hyphen or short dash were reduced to the form containing only spaces. Some spellings have been replaced, such as “huff ’n’ puff” to “huff and puff”. Bracketed terms, including markup tags, have been removed. All terms have been lower-cased in the preparatory materials and figures. For brevity, we will use the term “normalization” to refer to such preprocessing of terms.

The importance of normalization can be seen by the fact that the total number of unique author keywords reduced to lowercase only was 16,102 and 15,215 after the normalization procedure.

Examples of meaningful substitutions are the abbreviations EOR → enhanced oil recovery, CO₂ → carbon dioxide, CBM → coalbed methane, the plural reservoirs → reservoir, storages → storage, a term containing a hyphen two-phase flow → two phase flow, a keyword containing an abbreviation in parentheses enhanced oil recovery (EOR) → enhanced oil recovery.

Without normalization of the abstract texts and taking all 16,102 unique author keywords in their original spelling, only 9,502 of them occur in 8,051 abstract texts ($9,502 \times 100 / 16,102 = 59\%$).

This means that only 59% of the author keywords occur at least once in the abstract texts in their original spelling.

This can be an issue when selecting keywords to build queries for literature searches – experts select the articles they are looking for by their titles and abstracts. Also, the “Author Keyword” field may be less populated than the “Abstract” field in abstract databases.

Indexed keywords are not used in this paper, but for reference we note that despite the fact that there are more such words in each entry than author keywords and all entries are populated, unlike author keywords, their occurrence in the abstract texts is somewhat lower, amounting to about 51%.

When constructing the overall landscape of term co-occurrence using the VOSviewer program, the difference between the network of key terms in the original spelling and the normalized one is visually not very striking and requires a more detailed examination of the json files (available in supplementary materials) at

app.vosviewer.com. When analyzing particular network slices with the Scimago Graphica program, the difference is more noticeable.

Results and discussion

Comparison of author keywords clustering with and without term normalization

The easiest way to compare the clustering of author keywords with and without term normalization is to use the VOSviewer program and construct a co-occurrence network of author keywords for both cases.

The co-occurrence network of author keywords using the original values of the “Author Keywords” field and constructed using the following parameters: the total number of author keywords defined by the program is 16,102, of which 966 occur five or more times. Using 400 keywords with the highest overall strength of connections and a minimum cluster size of 50, five clusters were obtained, a fragment of which is shown in Fig. 1.

The issue of lack of keyword normalization is visible, for example, “enhanced oil recovery” and “EOR” are both found in the blue cluster, while “coalbed methane” and “CMB” are found in the green cluster.

For detailed review of this network, the file `AuKWsGrt4Top400Min50.json` placed in supplementary materials can be used at <https://app.vosviewer.com/>.

The network of co-occurrence of author keywords during normalization of terms of the “Author Keywords” field is constructed under the following parameters: the total number of normalized author keywords defined by the program is 15,215, of which 969 occur five or more times. Using 400 keywords with the greatest total link strength and minimum cluster size = 50, five clusters were obtained, a fragment of which is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Fragment of the co-occurrence network of the original author keywords

Рис. 1. Фрагмент сети совместной встречаемости исходных авторских ключевых слов

Fig. 2. Fragment of the co-occurrence network of normalized author keywords

Рис. 2. Фрагмент сети совместной встречаемости нормализованных авторских ключевых слов

There are notable similarities between Figs. 1 and 2. For example, the most commonly used terms “enhanced oil recovery”, “permeability” could still serve as the names of their clusters, but the term “heavy oil” got into the red cluster during normalization, while in the first figure it is in the purple cluster.

For detailed review of this network, the file `AuKWsGrt4Top400Min50norm.json` placed in supplementary materials can be used at <https://app.vosviewer.com/>.

Table 1 presents the terms in closely related clusters of author keywords obtained by the above two methods.

Table 1. Comparison of two clusters, conventionally labeled as “permeability”

Табл. 1. Сравнение двух кластеров, условно обозначенных как «permeability»

Normalized author keywords	Occurrence	Original author keywords	Occurrence
permeability	392	permeability	392
numerical simulation	250	numerical simulation	245
hydraulic fracturing	187	hydraulic fracturing	187
coalbed methane	125	shale gas	104
porous media	80	coalbed methane	99
enhanced geothermal system	71	horizontal well	88
shale	69	porous media	80
fracture	66	shale	63
natural gas hydrate	51	stress sensitivity	63
two phase flow	44	fracture	48
natural fracture	42	natural gas hydrate	48
tight gas reservoir	42	adsorption	45
depressurization	41	tight oil reservoirs	45
effective stress	40	depressurization	41
gas hydrate	38	effective stress	40
geothermal energy	35	hydraulic fracture	40
temperature	32	two-phase flow	37
mathematical model	31	geothermal energy	35
stimulated reservoir volume	30	enhanced geothermal system	34
finest migration	29	temperature	32
fracture propagation	29	mathematical model	31
gas production	28	apparent permeability	29
methane hydrate	28	finest migration	29
fracturing fluid	27	tight gas reservoir	29
pore network model	27	fracture propagation	28
coalbed methane reservoir	26	gas hydrate	28
modeling	26	gas production	28
supercritical carbon dioxide	26	stimulated reservoir volume	28
finite element method	25	low permeability reservoir	27
permeability anisotropy	24	methane hydrate	26

The terms “permeability”, “numerical simulation”, “hydraulic fracturing” having the same spelling occur in both columns with the same frequency. But already “coalbed methane”

occurs 125 times in the left column and 99 times in the right column. Similarly, “two-phase flow” – 44 and “two-phase flow” – 37 times and so on.

Table 2 presents the terms “reservoir simulation”, “relative permeability”, “machine learning” and “heterogeneity”, which consistently reflect a specific topic.

Normalization led to a change in the frequency of occurrence of the terms, but the topic they describe remained unchanged.

Table 2. Comparison of two clusters, conventionally labeled as “reservoir simulation”

Табл. 2. Сравнение двух кластеров, условно обозначенных как «reservoir simulation»

Normalized author keywords	Occurrence	Original author keywords	Occurrence
reservoir simulation	120	relative permeability	116
relative permeability	116	reservoir simulation	115
carbon dioxide storage	96	machine learning	90
machine learning	91	CO2 storage	85
heterogeneity	79	heterogeneity	79
carbon dioxide sequestration	72	CO2 sequestration	66
petroleum engineering	65	petroleum engineering	65
carbon dioxide injection	61	oil/gas reservoirs	58
oil/gas reservoir	58	sensitivity analysis	57
sensitivity analysis	57	capillary pressure	55
artificial neural network	55	viscosity	52
capillary pressure	55	waterflooding	52
carbon dioxide enhanced oil recovery	52	CO2 injection	50
viscosity	52	optimization	50
waterflooding	52	asphaltene	44
optimization	50	gas injection	43
asphaltene	45	reservoir characterization	43
in situ combustion	43	artificial neural network	41
reservoir characterization	43	carbon dioxide	40
history matching	40	deep learning	38
deep learning	38	history matching	35
recovery factor	29	CO2	32
artificial intelligence	28	asphaltene precipitation	31
genetic algorithm	28	unconventional reservoir	31
minimum miscibility pressure	28	tight reservoirs	28
bitumen	27	bitumen	27
carbon capture utilization storage	27	CCUS	27
numerical modeling	27	numerical modeling	27
unconventional petroleum	27	oil recovery factor	27
crude oil	26	unconventional petroleum	27

In the original records, the term “reservoir simulation” was referred to in both singular and plural, which caused the observed difference in the data columns; even more frequently, the term “artificial neural network” appears in both singular and plural.

On the other hand, terms with the single spelling “heterogeneity”, “viscosity”, “deep

learning”, “numerical modeling” and “bitumen” occur the same number of times in both columns.

An example of a significant difference in occurrence is the term “gas injection”, which appears on the right side of Table 2 and on the left side of Table 4.

The term “tight reservoir” does not appear in the cluster of normalized keywords, but it appears in the right-hand column in the plural “tight reservoirs”.

The term “waterflooding” appears 52 times in both columns of this table and in the spelling “water flooding” in Table 3. This term was not normalized in the process of preparing the author keywords.

Table 3. Comparison of two clusters, conventionally labeled as “enhanced oil recovery”

Табл. 3. Сравнение двух кластеров, условно обозначенных как «enhanced oil recovery»

Normalized author keywords	Occurrence	Original author keywords	Occurrence
enhanced oil recovery	563	enhanced oil recovery	384
heavy oil	194	EOR	147
carbonate reservoir	139	wettability	112
interfacial tension	115	wettability alteration	108
low permeability reservoir	114	carbonate reservoir	99
wettability	112	interfacial tension	92
wettability alteration	109	oil recovery	89
oil recovery	89	formation damage	73
steam assisted gravity drainage	78	surfactant	68
surfactant	78	polymer flooding	52
carbon dioxide	77	low permeability	50
formation damage	73	water flooding	47
heavy oil reservoir	68	carbonate reservoirs	40
carbon dioxide flooding	54	enhanced oil recovery (EOR)	39
nanoparticle	54	nanoparticles	36
polymer flooding	52	foam	35
water flooding	50	conformance control	34
imbibition	49	contact angle	34
microbial enhanced oil recovery	47	improved oil recovery	32
simulation	41	sweep efficiency	31
naturally fractured reservoir	37	core flooding	30
heterogeneous reservoir	36	low-permeability reservoirs	29
foam	35	recovery factor	29
oil reservoir	35	microbial enhanced oil recovery	25
carbonate rock	34	asphaltene deposition	23
conformance control	34	heavy oil reservoirs	22
contact angle	34	carbonate rock	21
core flooding	34	permeability reduction	21
air injection	32	nanofluid	20
asphaltene precipitation	31	salinity	20

In the right part of the table there are different spellings of the term: “enhanced oil recovery”, “EOR”, and “enhanced oil recovery (EOR)”, which can significantly affect the clustering results due to the wide use of this term.

The importance of writing the term with and without hyphen can be seen in this table. “low-permeability reservoir” occurs 114 times in the left column and “low-permeability reservoirs” occurs 29 times in the right column, while “low-permeability reservoir” occurs 27 times but already in Table 1.

The term “heavy oil reservoir” appears 68 times in the left column of Table 3 and 44 times in the right column of Table 4. In the right column of Table 3, this term appears 22 times in the plural form. This is an example of how refusing to normalize terms can lead to the same term appearing in different clusters in singular or plural form. The importance of normalization

to the singular is also shown by the fact that “nanoparticle” occurs 54 times on the left side, and “nanoparticles” 36 times on the right side of the Table 3.

The normalized and original terms presented in Table 4 differ slightly in their frequency of occurrence, similarly describing the topic of “tight oil reservoir”.

Table 4. Comparison of two clusters, conventionally labeled as “tight oil reservoir”

Табл. 4. Сравнение двух кластеров, условно обозначенных как «tight oil reservoir»

Normalized author keywords	Occurrence	Original author keywords	Occurrence
tight oil reservoir	116	heavy oil	192
horizontal well	107	tight oil reservoir	69
shale gas	107	CO2 flooding	52
fractured reservoir	81	imbibition	49
unconventional reservoir	69	heavy oil reservoir	44
stress sensitivity	66	simulation	41
low permeability	58	low-permeability reservoir	40
shale reservoir	52	unconventional reservoirs	38
hydraulic fracture	48	SAGD	34
adsorption	45	air injection	32
gas injection	43	geomechanics	32
improved oil recovery	33	fractured reservoirs	30
geomechanic	32	reservoir heterogeneity	30
fracture network	31	threshold pressure gradient	30
threshold pressure gradient	31	multiphase flow	29
shale gas reservoir	30	oil reservoir	28
apparent permeability	29	recovery	26
multiphase flow	29	steam injection	25
carbon dioxide huff n puff	27	water injection	24
diffusion	25	fractal theory	23
pressure transient analysis	25	analytical model	22
fractal theory	23	pressure transient analysis	22
huff n puff	23	heat transfer	20
flowback	19	steam flooding	20
production performance	19	flowback	19
dual porosity	18	numerical model	19
gas condensate	18	production performance	19
non darcy flow	18	thermal recovery	19
flow regime	16	water cut	19
rate transient analysis	16	water saturation	19

The most important thing to note in this table is that the term “heavy oil” is the most frequent term in the right column, but it appears in the left column in Table 3.

The terms “fractured reservoir” and “unconventional reservoir” occur in the singular in the left column, but in the plural in the right column.

The term “shale gas reservoir” does not appear in the right column.

In Table 5, the terms “shale oil” and “porosity” occur with equal frequency in the left

and right columns. However, the normalized value “nuclear magnetic resonance” occurs more frequently than the original, where it may appear as the abbreviation NMR.

Table 5. Comparison of two clusters, conventionally labeled as “shale oil” and “porosity”

Табл. 5. Сравнение двух кластеров, условно обозначенных как «shale oil» and «porosity»

Normalized author keywords	Occurrence	Original author keywords	Occurrence
nuclear magnetic resonance	156	shale oil	137
shale oil	137	porosity	114
porosity	114	Ordos Basin	113
Ordos Basin	113	pore structure	101
pore structure	101	tight oil	92
tight oil	94	NMR	74
tight sandstone	77	tight sandstone	70
tight reservoir	70	nuclear magnetic resonance	69
diagenesis	66	diagenesis	66
spontaneous imbibition	62	spontaneous imbibition	61
reservoir quality	58	reservoir quality	58
reservoir	56	fractured reservoir	51
shale oil reservoir	41	reservoir	50
Junggar Basin	40	tight reservoir	42
tight sandstone reservoir	37	Junggar Basin	40
sandstone	34	sandstone	33
biomarker	33	pore size distribution	31
pore size distribution	33	Sichuan Basin	31
Sichuan Basin	31	Tarim Basin	28
Tarim Basin	28	Yanchang Formation	28
Yanchang Formation	28	shale reservoir	27
controlling factor	27	carbonate	26
source rock	26	shale oil reservoir	24
oil shale	23	tight sandstone reservoir	24
lithofacy	22	controlling factors	23
reservoir rock	22	oil shale	22
fractal dimension	21	fractal dimension	21
reservoir characteristic	21	lithofacies	21
sandstone reservoir	21	reservoir characteristics	21
Songliao Basin	20	reservoir rock	20

This table is interesting because the lack of disclosure of abbreviations (NMR→nuclear magnetic resonance) can cause that the most frequently occurring term is different on the left and right side of the table.

This table lists the names of the basins “Ordos Basin”, “Junggar Basin”, “Sichuan Basin”, “Tarim Basin”, “Songliao Basin” – all

these basins are located in China. This is consistent with the large number of Chinese publications in the studied sample of bibliometric records.

It should be noted that the above tables only summarize the 30 most frequent terms from the full keyword occurrence tables, so the term occurrence amounts may not match.

The comparison of the terms in the tables above helped to illustrate the importance of term normalization on the results of term clustering.

The importance of term normalization will become even more evident in the next section.

Using the Scimago Graphica program to identify promising research tasks

Within the framework of this article, the promising research tasks are assumed to be described by the author keywords that occur more often in new publications that have a high citation rate and connection with other terms. Technically, this can be visualized as a slice of the network of co-occurrence of terms represented in the coordinates “Average publication year of the documents in which a keyword occurs” (avg. pub. year) and “Average normalized number of citations” (avg. norm. citations).

Let’s explain the concepts used by quoting from the VOSviewer manual: “Avg. norm. citations. The average normalized number of citations received by the documents in which a keyword or a term occurs... The normalized number of citations of a document equals the number of citations of the document divided by the average number of citations of all documents published in the same year and included in the data that is provided to VOSviewer”³.

For a better understanding of the content of the publications selected as examples, their titles and my abbreviated version of the abstract are given in the body of the paper; they are enclosed in quotation marks to emphasize that this is not plagiarism but citation.

³ van Eck N.J., Waltman L. Manual for VOSviewer version 1.6.20. URL: https://www.vosviewer.com/documentation/Manual_VOSviewer_1.6.20.pdf (accessed 20 February 2025).

Fig. 3 shows the graph of the term co-occurrence network constructed for author keywords taking into account their normalization. The following constraints were used to construct the graph in Scimago Graphica software: clusters 1, 2, 3 out of five obtained for normalized author keywords by VOSviewer software; total link strength ≥ 44 ; avg. norm. citations ≥ 1 ; degree ≥ 25 . Degree was calculated for the prebuilt network, then the data from this network was exported, the co-occurrence network was re-built using the exported data, and then the degree ≥ 25 filter was implemented to limit the number of terms displayed in the graph. This filter leaves only terms that are well related to other terms in the graph, which is important for identifying a local topic described by a number of co-occurring terms. An analogous result can be obtained by applying the “link strength” and “total link strength” filters to the original graph, but all these parameters are calculated for the network in question, so the resulting values may differ. In this case, the capabilities of Scimago Graphica were demonstrated. Filters are used to display only the terms most relevant to the analysis being performed to improve the readability of the graph in the publication.

The degree of a node is defined as the number of links it has with other nodes in the network.

According to the VOSviewer manual, “Total link strength attribute indicates the total strength of the links of an item with other items”⁴.

⁴ Ibid.

Short summary of the abstract: “Exposure of various nanofluids from zirconium dioxide (ZrO₂), calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), titanium dioxide (TiO₂), silicon dioxide (SiO₂), magnesium oxide (MgO), aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃), cerium oxide (CeO₂) and carbon nanotubes (CNT) on the wettability of carbonate rocks were investigated for enhanced oil recovery from oil reservoirs. The results of

spontaneous imbibition tests and core flooding experiments confirm the active role of CaCO₃ and SiO₂ nanoparticles in enhanced oil recovery. It is shown that both irreducible water saturation and inlet capillary pressure increased after treatment with CaCO₃ nanofluid.”

Fig. 4 shows a graph constructed under the same conditions as the previous one, but for the original author keywords.

Fig. 4. Co-occurrence network of the original author keywords with respect to the constraints presented in Fig. 3

Рис. 4. Сеть совместной встречаемости исходных авторских ключевых слов с учетом ограничений, представленных на рис. 3

The lack of normalization of term spelling affected the clustering. This is particularly noticeable for the second cluster in this figure. The term “methane hydrate” is not reflected on it, and it is found in articles with high citations according to the previous figure. In the third cluster, the terms “nanoparticles” and “nanofluids” are present, but the term “carbonates”, as in the previous figure, is not present, and it is found in more recent

publications. The first cluster in this figure does not contain the term “deep learning”, which is found in newer publications with good citations. If we refer to the interactive web page provided in supplementary materials, we can see those two spellings “enhanced oil recovery” and “enhanced oil recovery (EOR)” are presented in the graph. This example illustrates well the importance of preprocessing of the text fields on the obtained results.

Co-occurrence network analysis of terms in the text of abstracts

The VOSviewer program allows to build a co-occurrence network not only for author and index keywords, but also for terms presented in abstract texts. VOSviewer generates a list of noun phrases and brings the terms to the singular number, more details can be found in the manual of the program.

This approach to defining key terms works well, but in the text of abstracts of scientific papers it is quite often found abbreviations of the most commonly used terms in the given research area, e.g., EOR → enhanced oil recovery.

Therefore, the previously compiled list of abbreviations (thesaurus_terms.txt file) was used to construct a network of co-occurrence of terms in the abstract texts. It should be noted that VOSviewer performs whole term replacement, i.e. if in file thesaurus_terms.txt we specified that “EOR → enhanced oil recovery”, the term “CO₂ EOR process” will not be replaced, but the individual term “EOR” will be replaced by “enhanced oil recovery”. Going beyond this example, it is possible to perform an additional iteration of term normalization by analyzing the terms used to build the network and expanding the list of replacements in thesaurus_terms.txt. Another way is to perform term substitution in the original abstract text (or titles).

A private observation of the author of this paper shows that the use of textual fields of titles and abstracts is underestimated in many publications, the construction of a network of keywords is significantly more frequent. At the same time, the use of title and abstract fields to build a network of terms co-occurrence, in my opinion, gives more coherent clusters and their number is smaller.

The point is that subject matter experts assess the need for further study of an article not

by its keywords, but by its title and abstract. The abstract and title fields in the dataset we studied were filled in completely, while the author keywords had 1,470 blank fields out of 8,051 total fields.

Another example, exporting from OnePetro downloads titles and abstracts, but not keywords.

The situation is even worse for The Lens database: the query Filters: Year Published = (2024–2024) Subject = (Geochemistry and Petrology) received Scholarly Works (12,482). In 12,482 records a little more than half (6,851) of the abstracts are missing and almost all Keywords fields are empty (11,911).

Another example is using the “Publish or Perish” program, which can query a large number of resources, including OpenAlex, and the saved files have Title and Abstract fields, but no keywords.

Also, RSS feeds from topical sites have header and body fields, but not keyword fields.

For example, on the old Springer site (link.springer.com/search), you can use RSS with the fields: title and description (which includes an abstract), but not keywords.

According to the text fields of the given examples, it is possible to build a network of term co-occurrence and evaluate the topicality of the collected materials using VOSviewer.

In accordance with the above, Fig. 5 presents the network of co-currencies of the terms contained in the texts of the abstracts, taking into account the disclosure of abbreviations.

First cluster (red)

Most frequently appearing terms (Occurrences score): accuracy (499), stress (461), algorithm (384), horizontal well (326), hydraulic fracture (292), reservoir model (288), coal (280).

Fig. 5. Co-occurrence network of key terms used in the abstract texts, taking into account the disclosure of abbreviations

Рис. 5. Сеть совместной встречаемости ключевых терминов, содержащихся в текстах аннотаций, с учетом раскрытия сокращений

Terms most frequently used in new publications (Avg. pub. year score): marine hydrate reservoir (2023.1), extreme gradient (2022.6429), seepage field (2022.6), test set (2022.5455), extreme gradient boosting (2022.5), long short term memory (2022.4375), HBS (2022.4).

Here: HBS → hydrate-bearing sediment; in abstracts this term for the first time can meet with the decoding, and further used only as an abbreviation, it was not included in the list of exceptions, made from the author keywords.

Terms most frequently used in highly cited publications (Avg. norm. citations score): rock strength (3.1761), slip length (2.8046), CO₂ ECBM process (2.5662), gas property (2.5647), UGS (2.4861), hydrate bearing layer (2.4357), water permeability (2.4206)

Here: UGS → underground gas storage; in abstracts this term for the first time can meet with the decoding, and further used only as an abbreviation, it was not included in the list of exceptions, made from the author keywords.

Here: ECBM → enhanced coalbed methane, this term is present in the dictionary of abbreviations compiled using the author keywords, but it is part of a compound term, so it has not been modified. This feature should be taken into account when compiling the thesaurus_terms.txt file when performing term clustering based on title and abstract texts.

The abbreviations in the following clusters are similar and are not explained further.

Second cluster (green)

Most frequently appearing terms (Occurrences score): oil recovery (1,269), enhanced oil recovery (878), concentration (670), crude oil (630), viscosity (560), wettability (422), interfacial tension (410).

Terms most frequently used in new publications (Avg. pub. year score): dispersion stability (2022.6667), promising alternative (2022.4), microfluidic experiment (2022.25), imbibition efficiency (2022.2308), oilwater interfacial tension (2022.1818), MD simulation (2022.0833), experimental finding (2022). Here: MD → molecular dynamics.

Terms most frequently used in highly cited publications (Avg. norm. citations score): potential solution (2.9926), disjoining pressure (2.8678), viscoelastic property (2.5119), PAM (2.4066), nanotechnology (2.1721), early breakthrough (2.1437), CO₂ foam (2.1364). Here: PAM → polyacrylamide.

Third cluster (blue)

Most frequently appearing terms (Occurrences score): pore (749), content (487), sandstone (460), basin (450), hydrocarbon (434), dissolution (410), pore structure (348).

Terms most frequently used in new publications (Avg. pub. year score): development efficiency (2022.7857), shale oil resource (2022.7727), Qingshankou Formation (2022.3333), seepage capacity (2022.3214), basalt (2022.2308), movable oil (2022.1579), Baikouquan Formation (2022.125).

Terms most frequently used in highly cited publications (Avg. norm. citations score): macro pore (2.324), Winland (2.2597), pore geometry (2.198), pore distribution (2.185), burial history (2.1773), CT scanning (2.1137), host rock (2.1036). Here: CT → computed tomography.

Fourth cluster (khaki)

Most frequently appearing terms (Occurrences score): heavy oil reservoir (394), heavy oil (326), steam (246), oil recovery factor (197), oil viscosity (188), CO₂ flooding (158), solvent (154).

Terms most frequently used in new publications (Avg. pub. year score): underground hydrogen storage (2023.2609), hydrogen production (2023.1333), formation energy (2022.6429), nuclear magnetic resonance technology (2022.6), recovery degree (2022.5882), CO₂ storage efficiency (2022.4615), cushion gas (2022.4545).

Terms most frequently used in highly cited publications (Avg. norm. citations score): cushion gas (3.6855), underground hydrogen storage (3.5665), hydrogen storage (3.5626), hydrogen production (2.897), good potential (2.7012), CO₂ geological storage (2.317), residual trapping (2.2258).

The term “underground hydrogen storage” is more common in new highly cited publications, but the publications themselves are still few, so this term is not reflected in Figs. 6 and 7, where the term occurrence restriction is used.

Application of the Scimago Graphica program to identify promising research tasks using different restrictive filters

Below are the graphs plotted with Scimago Graphica software in the coordinates “Average normalized number of citations” and “Average publication year of the documents in which a keyword occurs” using different restriction filters.

Fig. 6 is plotted using the following sampling constraints: clusters 1, 2, 3; total link strength ≥ 100 ; occurrences ≥ 100 ; avg. norm. citations ≥ 1 .

The term “nanoparticle” often occurs with the terms “enhanced oil recovery”, “interfacial tension”, “wettability”, referring already to the same cluster.

A sequential search for the occurrence of terms in the text fields of all records yields: nanoparticle → 248, enhanced oil recovery → 145, interfacial tension → 69, wettability → 53, rock surface → 9.

The fact that a sequential search for the five terms yielded 9 results indicates the stability of the topic they are describing.

Of the nine articles, the most relevant is “Adsorption analysis of natural anionic surfactant for enhanced oil recovery: The role of mineralogy, salinity, alkalinity and nanoparticles” [17] which has 228 citations.

Short summary of the abstract: “Anionic surfactants are widely used as effective chemical reagents for enhanced oil recovery. This study deals with the equilibrium adsorption and kinetics of anionic surfactant synthesised from soapnut fruit on sandstone, carbonate and bentonite clay, which are reservoir rocks. The presence of alkali and nanoparticles reduces the loss of surfactant during adsorption and has a synergistic effect in reducing the interfacial tension, which is favourable for the application of surfactant in oil recovery”.

Fig. 7 is plotted using the following sampling constraints: clusters 1 and 3; total link strength ≥ 100 ; occurrences ≥ 20 ; avg. norm. citations ≥ 1.5 .

Fig. 7. Co-occurrence network of key terms used in the abstract texts, with respect to the constraints: clusters 1 and 3; total link strength ≥ 100 ; occurrences ≥ 20 ; avg. norm. citations ≥ 1.5

Рис. 7. Сеть совместной встречаемости ключевых терминов, содержащихся в текстах аннотаций, с учетом ограничений: кластеры 1 и 3; общая сила связи ≥ 100 ; occurrences ≥ 20 ; средняя нормализованная цитируемость $\geq 1,5$

This graph shows only the two clusters shown in Fig. 5 – the first and the third. A significant difference with Fig. 6 is that this data slice includes more rarely occurring terms (occurrences ≥ 20 vs. occurrences ≥ 100) and the threshold for the average normalized citation is raised (avg. norm. citations ≥ 1.5 vs. avg. norm. citations ≥ 1). Also note the slight shift of the right-most value on the average publication time axis (2022.8 vs. 2921.6).

Thus, this slice can be seen as a reflection of the more promising topics: there are not many publications yet, but they are more cited and published more recently.

For the sake of brevity, let us consider only one new topic that appeared in the first cluster and is described by the terms: methane hydrate, hydrate saturation, hydrate bearing sediment.

A sequential search for the occurrence of terms in the text fields of all records yields: methane hydrate \rightarrow 49, hydrate saturation \rightarrow 24, hydrate bearing sediment \rightarrow 5. Note that the number of publications is lower than in the examples in the previous figure.

Publication “Experimental study on the gas phase permeability of methane hydrate-bearing clayey sediments” [18] has been cited 74 times. Short summary of the abstract: “The permeability of hydrate-bearing sediments is one of the important parameters affecting the rate of gas production in hydrate reservoirs. In this paper, a series of experiments were conducted to investigate the gas-phase permeability of kaolin clay under different hydrate saturation. The results showed that the gas-phase permeability of kaolin clay firstly decreases and then increases with increasing hydrate saturation. The gas-phase permeability of hydrate-saturated clay samples at high effective axial stress is lower than that at low stress, which is due to pore space compaction.”

It was interesting to find the area of application of the method “extreme gradient boosting”; such publications turned out to be 18 such publications.

It was interesting to find the area of application of the “extreme gradient boosting” method. 18 such publications were found.

The most interesting article [19] has been cited 86 times. However, none of the 18 publication abstracts contained the term “hydrate”, suggesting that the inclusion of the term “extreme gradient boosting” in this cluster is due to co-occurrence with other terms, such as “permeability”, but not “hydrate”. The term “permeability” may be relevant in the context of records relating to “CBM recovery”, which in turn has a relationship to the term “methane hydrate”.

This example shows that a terms co-occurrence network, although a clear method for identifying relevant or promising research tasks, is not always convenient for extending literature collection by composing queries from co-occurring terms. For query generation, the direct method of determining the co-occurrence of terms (by algorithms like Apriori) may be more promising than assigning terms to a single cluster.

Conclusions

Despite the fact that the index keywords used in a query to Scopus is rarely found in author keywords and abstracts, bibliometric records exported by such a query are relevant to the given topic.

The given examples show the importance of preprocessing text fields before performing term clustering.

The expediency of disclosing the abbreviations of key terms when constructing the terms co-occurrence network encountered in the abstracts of publications by the VOSviewer program is shown.

The effectiveness of using filters in the Scimago Graphica program to construct a term co-occurrence network to identify promising research topics is demonstrated.

It has been observed that in some cases terms occurring in the same cluster are not the best choice for querying to expand the collection of publications on a given topic. It is proposed to conduct a separate study

on the use of Apriori class algorithms for this purpose.

Promising research tasks can be described by the following terms according to the bibliometric data used: 1) nanopore, shale oil, pore size, molecular; 2) nanoparticle, enhanced oil recovery, interfacial tension, wettability, rock surface; 3) methane hydrate, hydrate saturation, hydrate bearing sediments.

Author contributions

Boris N. Chigarev – conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, visualization, writing – review & editing.

Conflict of interests

The author declares no conflict of interests.

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ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИЕ РЕСУРСЫ ЗЕМНОЙ КОРЫ: ВЫЗОВЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ

Оригинальная статья
УДК [303.6+303.7]:001.8
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Демонстрация значимости предварительной обработки текстовых полей библиометрических записей для выявления перспективных исследовательских задач на примере данных Scopus по Petroleum Reservoir Engineering

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Аннотация. *Актуальность.* В настоящее время библиометрический анализ данных из реферативных баз часто используется для выявления актуальных исследовательских задач с целью рационального использования финансовых и других ресурсов. *Цель работы.* Продемонстрировать важность предварительной обработки текстовых полей библиометрических записей для построения сети совместной встречаемости терминов и возможность последующего использования Scimago Graphica для детального изучения различных срезов результатов кластеризации с целью выявления актуальных тем исследований. *Материалы и методы.* Использована 8051 запись, экспортированная из Scopus и соответствующая фильтру: (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD, "Petroleum Reservoir Engineering")) за последние десять лет. Для библиометрического анализа применялись программы VOSviewer и Scimago Graphica. *Результаты.* Показана релевантность использования фильтра «LIMIT-TO EXACTKEYWORD» в запросе к Scopus; целесообразность раскрытия сокращений в текстовых полях записей и предварительного уточнения текстов; эффективность использования фильтров в программе Scimago Graphica для построения сети сопряжения терминов с целью выявления перспективных тем исследований. *Выводы.* Выявленные в результате анализа перспективные темы исследований могут быть описаны следующими терминами: 1) нанопоры, сланцевая нефть, размер пор, молекулярный; 2) наночастицы и нанофлюиды; 3) гидрат метана, гидратонасыщенность и гидратоносные отложения. Замечено, что в некоторых случаях термины, встречающиеся в одном кластере, не являются лучшим выбором для запроса с целью расширения коллекции публикаций по данной теме. Поэтому для этой цели предлагается отдельное исследование с использованием алгоритмов класса ArXiv.

Ключевые слова: совместная встречаемость терминов, предварительная обработка текста, аббревиатуры, перспективные исследовательские задачи, VOSviewer, Scimago Graphica

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